

Data Management Plan (draft)

SINTEF, Maria Barrio

July-2020

Achieving wider uptake of water-smart solutions

Project number: 869283

Project duration: May 2020 – April 2024

H2020-SC5-2019-2

WWW.WIDER-UPTAKE.EU

D7.2 – Public

Data Management Plan (Draft)

VERSION

02

DATE

29-July-2020

ABSTRACT

This deliverable provides an easy overview of research data the project is expected to generate, the types and formats of this data, and how the data will be processed and stored to make them findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable, according to the principles of FAIR data management. The purpose of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is to contribute to good data handling during the project's lifetime, and to describe how data will be curated and preserved.

The DMP will be updated (and become more precise) as the project evolves. New versions will be created whenever important changes to the project occur (e.g. new data sets, changes in consortium policies, etc.). A final data management plan will be submitted at the end of the project (Deliverable D7.10, Month 48).

DELIVERABLE ID

D7.2

WORK PACKAGE

WP7

PLANNED DELIVERY DATE

31-July-2020

AUTHORSHIP AND APPROVAL INFORMATION

LEAD BENEFICIARY

SINTEF

AUTHOR(S)

Maria Barrio (SINTEF)

REVIEWED BY

Herman Helness (SINTEF)

RELEASE HISTORY

VERSION	DATE	VERSION DESCRIPTION/MILESTONE* DESCRIPTION
01	06-July-2020	Version released for PMT comments
02	29-July-2020	Revised draft version for submission

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1 Executive summary

WIDER UPTAKE aims at facilitating industrial symbiosis as a mean to increase resource efficiency, limit emissions and develop sustainable business based on water-smart solutions. During the project, WIDER UPTAKE will generate, collect, and reuse various types of research data.

The purpose of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is to contribute to good data handling through describing what research data the project expects to generate and which parts of the data that can be shared with the public. Furthermore, it gives instructions on naming conventions, metadata structure, storing of the research data and how to make public data available.

During the 48 active months of the project, a MS Teams / SharePoint¹ site will be used as the online working and collaboration platform. All datasets will be uploaded to this site and stored and handled in accordance with national and European rules on data protection and privacy. Metadata will be added to all datasets, and instructions on how to upload and store research data is provided in this document.

WIDER UPTAKE will use the open research data repository Zenodo to comply with the Horizon 2020 Open Access Mandate. This mandate applies to the underlying research data of publications, but beneficiaries can also voluntarily make other datasets open. In WIDER UPTAKE, all public deliverables and publications including "non-personal" related research data will be uploaded to the WIDER UPTAKE Community in Zenodo. Other datasets not directly linked to deliverables and publications that have the dissemination level "Public" will also be uploaded to Zenodo. Uploads will be done upon approval of the deliverables by the European Commission, upon publication or acceptance of scientific publications, or, for underlying datasets, at the end of the project at the latest.

Each dataset will be given a persistent identifier (Digital Object Identifier, DOI), supplied with relevant metadata, and linked to the project name and grant agreement number. Publications and underlying research data will be linked. Creative Common licenses will regulate reuse of the WIDER UPTAKE research data. Data security arrangements are defined for the SharePoint site and Zenodo.

Ethical aspects related to data collection, generation and sharing have been considered and nothing in this project shall be deemed to require a party to breach any mandatory statutory law under which the party is operating. This includes any national or European regulation, as well as rules and norms regarding ethics in conducting research.

The DMP is a living document and will be updated throughout the project to reflect the actual research data generated. The final version of the DMP will be made available at the end of the project and include instructions for how to access and reuse open research data from WIDER UPTAKE. Day-to-day data management and monitoring will be done using an online list in the SharePoint site that will be continuously updated to reflect actual data generation. The maintenance of this list is the responsibility of the Task 6.2 leader, under WP6.

¹ The Share Point platform will be accessible through a MS Teams portal.

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose of the document

The DMP provides an easy overview of research data the project is expected to generate, the types and formats of this data, and how this data is processed and stored to make them findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable, according to the principles of FAIR data management. The purpose of the DMP is to contribute to good data handling during the project's lifetime, and to describe how such data will be curated and preserved.

2.2 List of Definitions, Acronyms and Abbreviations

BibTeX	A reference management software for formatting lists of references.
CC licence	Creative Commons licenses are tools to grant copyright permissions to creative work.
CC-BY	This CC-license lets others distribute, remix, tweak, and build upon your work, even commercially, if they credit you for the original creation. This is the most accommodating of licenses offered. Recommended for maximum dissemination and use of licensed materials.
CC-BY-NC	This CC-license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work non-commercially, and although their new work must also acknowledge you and be non-commercial, they don't have to license their derivative works on the same terms.
CC-BY-SA	This CC-license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work even for commercial purposes, if they credit you and license their new creations under the identical terms. This license is often compared to "copyleft" free and open source software licenses. All new works based on yours will carry the same license, so any derivatives will also allow commercial use.
CSL	Citation Style Language An open XML-based standard to format citations and bibliographies.
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR data	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable data
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation. Regulation (EU) 2016/679.
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation An open-standard file format.
MARCXML	An XML schema based on the common MARC21 standards
OAI-PHM	The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting.
Research data	Refers to information, facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings, and images.
REST API	REST is an architectural style that defines a set of constraints to be used for creating web services. API means Application Programming Interface

SSL/TLS	Secure Sockets Layer / Transport Layer Security These are protocols offering secure communication on the internet.
Zenodo	Zenodo is a catch-all research data repository that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share research results, make research results citable, and search and reuse open research results from other projects. Zenodo is harvested by the OpenAIRE portal and hosted by the CERN cloud infrastructure.

2.3 Intended readership

Internally in the project:

- Project participants who are responsible for, or in any way involved with, data collection and data handling should use this document for instructions on how to handle, store and process data.
- All project participants can use this document to get an overview of data collected in the project and how this is processed, stored and made accessible.

External audience:

- The **Data Summary** and **FAIR Data Management** sections can be used by all relevant stakeholders who are interested in WIDER UPTAKE related activities and research topics to get an overview of the data collected in the project, how to access this data, and, if applicable, how to re-use this data in their own activities.
- [to be updated in Month 6] The **Ethics** section can be used by external voluntary participants in pilot/testing/demonstration activities in WIDER UPTAKE to learn about how the project will handle and store data in accordance with standards for ethics, privacy and security.

2.4 Structure of this document

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 1 is an introduction chapter describing the main purpose of the DMP.
- Section 2 provides an overview of the research data in the WIDER UPTAKE project, with details on types, formats, origin, and metadata provisions.
- Section 3 describes how the WIDER UPTAKE project will comply with the principles of FAIR data management and H2020 Open Access Mandate
- Section 4 describes the resources allocated to making data FAIR and open.
- Section 5 deals with ethical aspects related to data management in the WIDER UPTAKE project.

The online tool DMP Online, hosted by Data Curation Centre, has been used to generate content for this document². The tool is based on the Horizon 2020 DMP template and guidelines for FAIR data management in Horizon 2020³.

2.5 Relationship with other deliverables

The DMP is not a fix document but evolves during the lifespan of the project. Deliverable D7.2 is the initial version of the WIDER UPTAKE Data Management Plan. D7.10 Data management plan, due in month 48 will be the final version of this document.

² https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/about_us

³ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

This document is complemented by the following deliverables:

- D7.1 Quality assurance plan
- D7.4 Communication plan
- D6.1 Updated dissemination and exploitation plan
- D8.1 H – Requirement No. 1

3 Data Summary

3.1 Purpose of the data collection and generation

WIDER UPTAKE aims at facilitating industrial symbiosis as a mean to increase resource efficiency, limit emissions and develop sustainable business based on water-smart solutions.

The overall motivation for data collection in WIDER UPTAKE is to:

- Perform technical and economic evaluations and validations of technologies and solutions based on field observations
- Understand the effect on quality of human life of water-smart solutions
- Perform reliable risk evaluations
- Facilitate learning and innovation uptake
- Increase the knowledge on institutional drivers and barriers
- Run optimization and multi-criteria decision-making models with data points from one or more cases
- Understand the nature of solutions and decision variables as input to sustainability models
- Calculate mass & energy balances to get environmental impact values
- Understand costs involved in the technological interventions
- Gain understanding of preferences of stakeholders for different criteria to be used in a multi-criteria decision-making models;
- Track long term behaviour change with respect to sustainability for pilot user
- Develop and improve a governance assessment tool
- Develop industrial networks and ensure experience-sharing across cases
- Explore innovative business models
- Enable assessment of how water smart different symbiotic solutions are and how they contribute to progress towards the Sustainable Development Goals.
- Gather feedback to improve results, technologies, and solutions
- Increase awareness and user acceptance of water-smart solutions, and provide new knowledge to encourage behaviour change.

The project will generate and reuse various types of data. Table 2, on page **Error! Bookmark not defined.**, provides a list of all datasets currently expected to be generated in the WIDER UPTAKE project and their planned accessibility. We recognise that this list will develop and grow as the project evolves.

Only data that is needed to perform project activities will be collected, and as far as possible, participants will not be asked to provide personal data unless this is necessary.

3.2 Data types, formats and size

The WIDER UPTAKE project will mainly use widely accepted formats for data generation, such as:

- **Documents/Reports/Publications:** .PDF/A, txt, doc/docx
- **Spreadsheets:** .xls/.xlsx
- **Databases:** .csv, TXT, ACDB
- **Audio files:** .mp3, .wav, .wma, .ra

- **Pictures:** jpg, png
- **Video:** avi, flv, mov, mp4, wmv
- **Models:** .mat, .slx, .lyt

Some of the data WIDER UPTAKE will collect and generate is classified as *personal data*, such as names, surnames, e-mail addresses, IP addresses, etc. In addition, we will collect data that are person-related, even if they are not personal or sensitive. Interview material, for instance, that can be connected to a person by name, age, professional role, address or even just IP address must be kept and treated confidentially according to the GDPR. This data must be irreversibly anonymised before being made public. If such data cannot be irreversibly anonymised, it will remain confidential and only managed by designated Data Controllers in the project. If a partner who is not a Data Controller needs access to process personal data (Data Processor), an assessment of this will be done by the Data Controller and if granted a specific Data Processing Agreement will be set up between the Data Controller and the partner requesting access. A template for Data Processing Agreement is provided in appendix A. Non-anonymous data, although not openly shared in the project or beyond, can still provide input to deliverables and publications. Only anonymised data or analysis of the aggregated data, containing no details that can be linked to individual participants, will be made public.

The size of the data will vary, and the size of the raw data files might be large for some of the pilots. However, the size of the processed data is expected to be moderate and should not represent challenges regarding storage capacity or handling.

3.3 SharePoint and metadata provision

All datasets in the WIDER UPTAKE project will be stored in a SINTEF MS Teams /SharePoint project site. This will be the projects online collaboration area during the 48 months the project is active. Each partner will be responsible for uploading the datasets they have collected/generated. Each dataset will be catalogued in a list providing an overview of all datasets in the project, as well as uploaded to a dedicated research data folder in the MS Teams/SharePoint site. All datasets will use standard SharePoint version control and access control is available to enable limited access to certain types of data.

These metadata will be provided for each data set:

- File name
- Date
- Version
- File type
- Description
- WP number
- Responsible person
- Lead
- Dissemination level

In addition, all data on the WP2 database server will be stored on Synology Disk Station Manager (DSM). It has Military Grade Shared Folder Encryption to secure business data from potential malicious users, DSM adopts the AES 256-bit military grade encryption technology to store your data in a format protected by an encryption key. Connecting a NAS to the Internet greatly increases its convenience and possible uses, but caution must be exercised to protect it from outside attacks. With DSM, you can block unusual attempts to enter your NAS in a highly customizable manner.

3.4 Zenodo

Zenodo is a "catch-all" open research data repository which gathers research data across all disciplinary fields. It is for non-military purposes only, and the repository is hosted and managed by CERN. All data deposited to Zenodo is stored securely in the CERN Data Centre's cloud infrastructure⁴ (see section 5.2).

WIDER UPTAKE will use the open research data repository *Zenodo* to comply with the H2020 Open Access Mandate⁵. All scientific publications, including public deliverables and public parts of underlying datasets will be uploaded to the *WIDER UPTAKE Community*⁶ in Zenodo. In addition, the project will upload other datasets (not directly linked to publications and deliverables) with dissemination level "Public" and make them openly accessible via Zenodo.

3.5 Instructions for uploading datasets

Table 1 and Figure 1 provide instructions to project participants on how to upload datasets to SharePoint and Zenodo:

Table 1: Instructions for uploading datasets to SharePoint and Zenodo

Upload instructions – WIDER UPTAKE MS Teams / SharePoint Site
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please upload all relevant WIDER UPTAKE data sets to this folder in the WIDER UPTAKE MS Teams/ Sharepoint site: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Research data for open access ZENODO • Use this naming convention (for details see 3.1.5): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Descriptive text H2020_WIDERUPTAKE_DeliverableNumber_UniqueDataNumber</i> ○ <i>Descriptive text H2020_WIDERUPTAKE_PublicationNumber_UniqueDataNumber</i> • Be sure to use the same file name when uploading later versions • Register mandatory metadata on your data set by adding a new item to this list: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ WIDER UPTAKE Register of mandatory metadata
Upload instructions - Zenodo
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research data underlying scientific publications/classified as "Public" should, in addition, be uploaded to the WIDER UPTAKE Community in Zenodo. To do this you must complete the following steps: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Create a profile in Zenodo to be able to upload files ○ Click on the WIDER UPTAKE <i>Community</i> link above, or search for "WIDER UPTAKE" under the "Communities" tab at the top of the Zenodo site ○ On the Community site, click the green "New upload" button in the top right corner ○ Enter requested data and confirm the upload. The information requested is located in the metadata list on MS Teams / SharePoint (WIDER UPTAKE Register of mandatory metadata) ○ Remember to add the European Commission community in the box labelled "communities". You can use the search function to locate the community and add it. The data will then automatically be uploaded to both communities, so you don't have to do it twice. • Uploading should be done as soon as possible and at the latest on article publication or EC approval of deliverables for underlying datasets. Other datasets will be uploaded in the final month of the project at the latest. • Each partner is responsible for uploading data sets collected/generated by them. If needed, T7.1 task leader in WP7 will supply assistance.

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/>

⁵ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/communities/wider-uptake/?page=1&size=20>

Figure 1 Process for uploading datasets

4 FAIR Data Management

WIDER UPTAKE will manage data in accordance with the principles of **FAIR data management**⁷ (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable data) The project aims to maximise access to, and re-use of research data generated by the project. At the same time, there are datasets, or parts of datasets, generated in this project that cannot be shared due to commercial or IPR reasons. Table 2 provides a current overview of the expected datasets in the WIDER UPTAKE project and their accessibility.

4.1 Making data findable

4.1.1 WIDER UPTAKE Community in Zenodo

WIDER UPTAKE will use the Zenodo repository as the main tool to make our research data findable in accordance with the H2020 Open Access Mandate.

A *WIDER UPTAKE* community has been established in the Zenodo repository, and the project will upload all our public datasets and deliverables as well as scientific publications to this community. In addition, we will link all our uploads to the *European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE)* community for maximum findability. All uploads will be enriched with standard Zenodo metadata, including Grant Number and Project WIDER UPTAKE. Zenodo provides version control and assigns DOIs to all uploaded elements.

4.1.2 Metadata in Zenodo

Metadata associated with each published data set in Zenodo will by default be as follows:

- Digital Object Identifiers
- Version numbers
- Bibliographic information
- Keywords
- Abstract/description
- Associated project and community
- Associated publications and reports
- Grant information (project name, GA number, call identifier)
- Access and licensing info
- Language

4.1.3 Versioning and Digital Object Identifiers (DOI)

Zenodo provides DOI versioning of all datasets uploaded to their communities, which allows us to edit and update the uploaded datasets after they have been published. This also allows us to cite specific versions of an upload and cite all versions of an upload. As an example, DOI versioning of an uploaded software package that is released in two versions can look like this⁸:

- v1.0 (specific version): 10.5281/zenodo.60943
- v1.1 (specific version): 10.5281/zenodo.800648
- Concept (all versions): 10.5281/zenodo.705645

⁷ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

⁸ <http://help.zenodo.org/> (DOI versioning)

The first two DOIs for versions v1.0 and v.1.1 represent the specific versions of the software. The last DOI represents all the versions of the given software package, i.e. the concept of the software package and the ensemble of versions. They are therefore also referred to as *Version DOIs* and *Concept DOIs*, but technically they are both normal DOIs.

This does not, however, mean that you will receive a new DOI each time you edit the metadata related to your upload (e.g. change the title of a file or dataset). A new DOI version will only be created if you update the actual files you have uploaded.

4.1.4 Approach to search keywords

Each partner who collects and generates public datasets will be responsible for uploading these to Zenodo and to assign specific search keywords relevant to these datasets. Dataset specific keywords must be descriptive to the content of the dataset. E.g., a dataset containing information on user acceptance of a solution should be tagged with corresponding keywords such as, "*Solution*"/"*user acceptance*". In addition, the project has defined a set of general keywords that apply to all public datasets, scientific publications and public deliverables. These are as follows:

- Water recycling and reuse
- Environment, resources and sustainability
- Circular economy
- Sustainability transition
- Symbiosis between industry and water utilities

4.1.5 Naming conventions

Data will be named using the following naming conventions:

Descriptive text_H2020_WIDER_UPTAKE_DeliverableNumber_UniqueDataNumber
Descriptive text_H2020_WIDER_UPTAKE_PublicationNumber_UniqueDataNumber

Explanation of the naming convention:

- "Descriptive text" refers to a *short* description of the content of the dataset (see example)
- "Acronym" refers to the project's short name or acronym; WIDER_UPTAKE
- "DeliverableNumber" refers to the deliverable number as described in the DoA
- "PublicationNumber" refers to the number the publication has in the project internal directory of all publications from the project
- "UniqueDataNr" is the number automatically generated by the research metadata list in SharePoint (see section 2.5)

Example of dataset name:

- APP user acceptance_H2020_WIDER_UPTAKE_D1.1_003
- Weather data OSL Jan 2019_H2020_WIDER_UPTAKE_D7.2_017

4.2 Making data accessible

The H2020 Open Access Mandate aims to make research data generated by H2020 projects accessible with as few restrictions as possible, but also accept protection of personal or sensitive data due to privacy concerns and/or commercial or security reasons.

Pilot project business data regarding material proportions, properties, costs and prices have to be protected at least until the company is comfortable with releasing data or they have acquired patents.

All public datasets, scientific publications and deliverables will be uploaded to Zenodo and made openly available, free of charge. Publications and underlying data sets will be linked through use of persistent identifiers (DOI versioning). Data sets with dissemination level "confidential" (non-anonymous datasets) will not be shared due to privacy/ethical concerns. Potentially, some datasets might be restricted due to protection for commercial exploitation. If such cases arise during the project, this will be informed in the final version of the DMP. All non-proprietary data will also be public-accessible through the Virtual Learning Centre, to be delivered at the end of project.

Metadata including licences for individual data records as well as record collections will be harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API. The data will be available through www.zenodo.org, and hence accessible using any web browsing application. No specific software or hardware is needed to access and reuse the data.

Table 2 below provides a list of all datasets expected to be generated in the WIDER UPTAKE project and their planned accessibility. This list constitutes the first version of dataset description and we recognise that it will develop and grow as the project evolves. In addition, some information concerning the datasets currently remain unknown, e.g. size of the datasets. An updated version of the list containing all dataset details will be provided at the end of the project.

Table 2 Overview of datasets in WIDER UPTAKE

WP	Task	Name of dataset	Description/Purpose	Format	Responsible	Origin	Class	Comments
1	All	Automatically collected data from measuring systems. Automated data collection through models running in participants' computer Related laboratory and analytical work. Description of pilot sites and processes.	Experimental data from pilot activities at 7 locations: Hamar (NO), Stavanger (NO), Accra (GH), Corleone (IT), Marineo (IT), Prague (CZ) and Amsterdam (NL).		CASE OWNERS		PU	The raw source data might be very large datasets. Subject to approval from case owners.
1	1.4	CCTV Visual observations Timelapse with chart of the influence	Camera observing the field, Timelapse, observing the growth (quality impact)		CVUT		PU	The raw data might be very large datasets.
1	All	Cost data	Costs information allowing evaluation of the recycling technology vs quality and risks		CASE OWNERS		CO	Subject to approval from case owners.
All	All	Interviews with groups and individual participants in the pilots/demonstrations/etc. at each site	Interviews, questionnaires, surveys, audio recordings from live stakeholder sessions to understand stakeholders and their perspectives		ALL		CO	Subject to approval from case owners.
2		Papers and literature review, precedent studies, Interview and questionnaires, legislation, database and statistical studies	Data collection for a qualitative analysis in first place.	PDF, CSV, JPEG, DOC	ALL		PU	
3		Literature reviews, databases, statistics	Existing data: • Grey and white literature from past studies and reports	CSV, PDF, DOC, JPEG	ALL		PU	

D7.2 Data management plan (Draft)

		<p>Intervention option data on substances, efficiencies, energy, etc.</p> <p>Health/policy standards documents</p> <p>Material/water reuse properties and applications</p> <p>Process technology specification sheets</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative parameter values from past research <p>Manually collected data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interviews, surveys, questionnaires Feedback from participants in stakeholder sessions Data from site of intervention related to use, parameters, production, energy use, etc. Feedback from user of pilot/demonstration (short and long-term) 					
		Modelling data	Automatically collected as output of models		ALL		PU	
4	4.1	Literature review (preceding studies/frameworks, public documents)	Background for development of governance assessment tool	.doc, mp3, PDF	ALL	Existing data: - Grey and white literature from past studies Public policy and planning documents	PU	
4	4.1	Stakeholder interviews	Develop and improve the governance assessment tool, validate the results from the respective case assessments.	.doc, mp3, PDF	SINTEF	Semi-structured interviews (phone, video or face-to-face)	CO	May be linked to persons.
4	4.1	Field observations and workshop data.	Develop and improve the governance assessment tool, validate the results from the respective case assessments.	.doc, mp3, and PDF	SINTEF	Participant observation during workshops and visits to the	CO	May be linked to persons.

						demonstration sites.		
4	4.2	Documentation of process for network and business model development in connection with each demonstration case (x5)	Network and business model development.	.doc, mp3, PDF,	SINTEF	Action research and interaction during workshops.	CO	Subject to approval from partners
4	4.3	Documentation of process to elaborate and test innovative business models.	Develop scenarios and test selected business models.	.doc, mp3, PDF	SINTEF	Workshop interaction, interviews	CO	Subject to approval from partners
4	4.4	Policy mix and pathway findings	Discuss/identify transition pathways.	.doc, mp3, PDF	SINTEF	Existing data (public documents, preceding research) Workshop interaction.	PU	
5	5.1	Framework for water smartness with objectives, criteria and indicators	Will be used to organise data from the evaluation of the different solutions that are demonstrated in the case studies.	.xls	SINTEF	Literature and workshops	PU	Planned for publication in open access
5	5.3	Framework for water smartness with objectives, criteria and indicators adapted to the local conditions in the 5 case studies.	Data from the case studies to be used in evaluation of the different solutions that are demonstrated.	.xls	SINTEF	Literature and workshops	PU	Planned for publication in open access
6	6.1.1	Dataset on objectives, solutions, drivers, pressures and trends related to achieving a water-smart society from discussions in the CoP completed.	Provide a general analysis of the state condition towards a water smart society	.cvs	UNIPA	Survey / interview/literature review	PU	Subject to approval from partners
6	6.1.2	Report from scenario Analysis	Provide the future scenarios of a water smart systems	PDF	UNIPA	Analysed output of mathematical models	PU	Subject to approval from partners

D7.2 Data management plan (Draft)

6	6.1.4 6.1.5	Roadmap tool	Web-base tool to support the achieving of a water smart system	MATLAB/ Simulink files(*.mat / .slx)	SINTEF	Data collected from other WPS	PU	Useful for water society in order to achieve as much as possible water smart systems
6	6.1.4 6.1.5	Roadmap report	Report describing the roadmap structure and features	PDF	SINTEF	Roadmap use	PU	Useful to know how to use the roadmap
6	6.2.1	Dissemination and exploitation plan	Summary of actions (e.g. meetings with stakeholders) to promote novel industrial symbiosis among the involved industrial stakeholders and the creation of new companies to commercialize the materials recovered during the project	PDF	SINTEF	Survey / interview/literature review/data analysis	PU	Subject to approval from partners
6	6.2.2	Virtual Learning and Sharing Centre	A tool to integrate, harmonize and coordinate innovation and demonstration of water-smart solutions and disseminate relevant knowledge		SINTEF		PU	Allow the spread of knowledge acquired during the project.
6	6.3.1	Dissemination documents	Summary documents of the different level of dissemination (Workshop; conference)	PDF	ALL	Meetings and dissemination events	PU	Allow to spread the core topics and idea of the project
6	6.3.2	Priority list of recommendations	These recommendations will represent a response to “what” and “how” responsible actors have to operate in view of obtaining specific objectives and results	PDF	PARTNER	Data analysis of the roadmap output	PU	Subject to approval from partners
6	6.1	Roadmap database	Input file to the roadmap, collected from all other WPs	.csv	PARTNER S	Data collected during the activities of the other WPs	PU	Subject to approval from partners
6	6.1	Results of the roadmap applications	Report on the result of roadmap use	PDF	PARTNER S		PU	Subject to approval from partners

7	7.1	Project coordination update	Information regarding the administrative issues in the project	.doc, .xls	SINTEF		CO	Document Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
7	7.2	Records of process interaction and feedback during Communities of Practice development	Develop Communities of Practice Facilitate industrial symbiosis Increase awareness and user acceptance, and provide new knowledge to encourage behaviour change.		SINTEF	Workshops and supplementary interviews	CO	Subject to approval from partners
7	7.2	Records from open/public Community of Practice events	Facilitate industrial symbiosis Increase awareness and user acceptance, and provide new knowledge to encourage behaviour change.		ALL	Workshops, seminars, web meetings	PU	
7		Contact information	Project internal and external stakeholders/participants in pilots/workshops/evaluation activities.	.xls, .doc	ALL		CO	Subject to approval from partners

4.3 Making data interoperable

Zenodo uses JSON schema as the internal representation of metadata and offers export to other formats such as Dublin Core, MARCXML, BibTeX, CSL, DataCite and export to Mendeley. The data record metadata will utilise the vocabularies applied by Zenodo. For certain terms, these refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef) and grants (OpenAIRE). Reference to any external metadata is done with a resolvable URL.

4.4 Reusable data

The WIDER UPTAKE project will enable third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) all public data sets, and regulate this by using Creative Commons Licences.

4.4.1 Recommended Creative Commons (CC) licences

WIDER UPTAKE will use Creative Commons licences (CC), which are tools to grant copyright permissions to creative work. As a default, the CC-BY-SA license will be applied for public WIDER UPTAKE research data. This license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work even for commercial purposes, as long as they credit you and license their new creations under the identical terms. This license is often compared to “copyleft”, free and open source software licenses. With this licence all new work based on WIDER UPTAKE data and results will carry the same license, so any derivatives will also allow commercial use. This does not preclude the use of less restrictive licenses as CC-BY or more restrictive licenses as CC-BY-NC, which does not allow commercial usage. This will be assessed in each case.

4.4.2 Availability and longevity of the WIDER UPTAKE research data sets

4.4.2.1 *Public (anonymous) data*

For data published in scientific journals, the underlying data will be made available no later than by journal publication. The data will be linked to the publication. Data associated with public deliverables will be shared once the deliverable has been approved and accepted by the EC. For other public datasets not directly linked to a scientific publication or deliverable, such datasets will be made available upon assessment by the responsible partner that it is ready for publishing, and in the final month of the project at the latest.

Open data can be reused in accordance with the Creative Commons licences. Data classified as confidential will as default not be reusable due to privacy/security concerns.

The public data will remain reusable via Zenodo for at least 20 years. This is currently the lifetime stated by the host laboratory CERN. In the event that Zenodo has to close their operations, they have provided a guarantee that they will migrate all content (including metadata) to other suitable repositories.

Interview data in anonymized form, that is with personal references removed, should also be kept, confidentially, for longer than 4 months – at least one year.

4.4.2.2 *Confidential (non-anonymous) data*

All non-anonymous data will be deleted at the end of the project. In case permission is given by the party providing and owning the data, some non-anonymous data will be kept for a maximum of 4 months after the

contractual end date of the project⁹. The additional 4 months is to keep the underlying datasets available to allow the completion of any scientific publications being prepared towards the end of the project.

An exemption is pictures and videos, taken with consent from voluntary project/pilot/workshop/exercise participants, that are used for communication purposes. If consent is *not* withdrawn at an earlier time, such data will be kept for up to 4 years after the end of the project in order to comply with the EC contractual obligation to continue dissemination, communication and exploitation activities after the project ends. If a party withdraws the consent to use this material (pictures, videos), it will be deleted without delay.

4.4.2.3 Classification of research outputs

The process of classifying research outputs from the WIDER UPTAKE project follows the guidelines provided in the "*H2020 Guidance for the classification of information in research projects*"¹⁰.

⁹ At present, the contractual end date of the WIDER UPTAKE project is: 2024-04-30. However, changes can be made to this date during the project (e.g. in case of a project extension) and the final version of the DMP will provide the exact date.

¹⁰ H2020 Programme. *Guidance for the classification of information in research projects*. Version 2.1. 26 October 2016.

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/hi/secur/h2020-hi-guide-classif_en.pdf

5 Allocation of resources

5.1 Costs

WIDER UPTAKE uses standard tools and a free of charge research data repository. The costs of data management activities are limited to project management costs and will be covered by allocated resources in the project budget.

Long-term preservation of the public data is ensured through Zenodo. Other resources needed to support reuse of data after the project ends will be solved on a case-by-case basis.

5.2 Data Manager

The overall responsibility for data management lies with the WP 7 Leader, who is Maria Barrio from SINTEF.

6 Data Security

In this chapter, the security features of the research data infrastructure used to store and handle data in the WIDER UPTAKE project are described.

6.1 Active Project - Data security as specified for SINTEF SharePoint

SINTEF MS Teams/SharePoint is the online collaboration platform used the WIDER UPTAKE project. A dedicated project site has been established on this platform, accessible only by the partner representatives in the consortium, through a MS Teams portal. Furthermore, a dedicated folder for research datasets is set up, allowing for stricter access control than the main project site.

The WIDER UPTAKE MS Teams / Sharepoint site has the following security settings:

- Access level: Restricted to persons (project members only). Further access restrictions on specific folders is enabled.
- Encryption with SSL/TLS protects data transfer between partners and the SINTEF SharePoint site.
- Threat management, security monitoring, and file-/data integrity prevents and/or registers possible manipulation of data.

Documents and elements in the SINTEF MS Teams / SharePoint sites are stored in Microsoft's cloud solutions, based in Ireland and the Netherlands. There will be no use of data centres in the US or outside EU/EEA and associated countries¹¹.

Nightly back-ups are handled by SINTEF's IT operations contractor. As a baseline, all project data will be stored for 10 years according to SINTEF's ICT policy, unless otherwise agreed in contracts and data processing agreements.

6.2 Repository - Data security as specified for Zenodo

The following list describes the security settings for Zenodo:

- Versions: Data files are versioned. Records are not versioned. The uploaded data is archived as a Submission Information Package. Derivatives of data files are generated, but original content is never modified. Records can be retracted from public view; however, the data files and records are preserved.
- Replicas and file preservation: All data files are stored in the CERN Data Centres, primarily Geneva, with replicas in Budapest. Data files are kept in multiple replicas in a distributed file system, which is backed up to tape on a nightly basis.
- Retention period: Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. The host laboratory of Zenodo CERN, has defined a lifetime for the repository of the next 20 years minimum.
- Functional preservation: Zenodo makes no promises of usability and understandability of deposited objects over time.
- Fixity and authenticity: All data files are stored along with an MD5 checksum of the file content.
- Files are regularly checked against their checksums to assure that file content remains constant.
- Succession plans: In case of closure of the repository, a guarantee has been made from Zenodo to migrate all content to suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.

¹¹ EEA = Norway, Iceland, Liechtenstein

7 Ethical Aspects (section to be updated in Month 6)

The proposed work in WIDER UPTAKE will fully comply with the regulations set out in Regulation (EU) 2016/679, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹². In addition, WIDER UPTAKE comply with the principles of the European Charter for Researchers, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, including ethical standards and guidelines, regardless country in which research is carried out.

Nothing in this project shall be deemed to require a party to breach any mandatory statutory law under which the party is operating. This includes any national or European regulations, rules and norms regarding ethics in conducting research.

7.1 Contact information

7.1.1 Use of e-mail addresses in WIDER UPTAKE MS Teams / SharePoint Site

An e-mail address is by definition personal information and covered by GDPR. The e-mail addresses of project participants are stored in the WIDER UPTAKE MS Teams / SharePoint Site. Only the project participants invited will have access. The e-mail address is a prerequisite to access the projects working area. By accepting the MS Teams / SharePoint invitation the participants consent to use and store their e-mail address for the purpose of online collaboration in the project.

The email-addresses will be deleted when access to the project area is no longer needed. SINTEF has signed GDPR data processing agreements with both Microsoft and the IT operations contractor handling our SharePoint platform.

7.2 Pictures and videos for communication purposes

WIDER UPTAKE will collect pictures and videos for use in communication activities (website, newsletter, social media). Such data will only be collected with prior consent from the people involved and only used for as long as consent is given. Pictures and video can contain personal data if an individual is the focus of the image or video. Examples include: 1) pictures/video of individuals stored together with personal details (e.g. identity cards); 2) pictures/video of individuals posted on the project website along with biographical details; 3) individual images published in a newsletter. Examples of pictures and video that is unlikely to contain personal data are: 1) pictures/video where people are incidentally included in an image or are not the focus (e.g. at a big conference/workshop); 2) images of people who are no longer alive (the GDPR only applies to living people).

When collecting pictures and video WIDER UPTAKE will follow established guidance and best practice on collecting and processing such data to ensure that we adhere to the legal requirements (e.g. guidance established by the University of Reading, UK¹³). Under no circumstances will pictures containing personal information be publicly shared without the subject's explicit consent.

The WIDER UPTAKE project partners are obliged by European and national law (GDPR) to protect personal data.

The coordinator of the WIDER UPTAKE project, SINTEF, follow ethical guidelines in its work, and *all* work conducted by SINTEF is subject to the SINTEF Ethics Council and the appointed Ethics Representative. Important aspects with respect to this are:

¹² Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>

¹³ <https://www.reading.ac.uk/internal/imps/DataProtection/DataProtectionRequirements/imps-d-p-photographic.aspx>

- The ethical guidelines are based on the vision of using science and technology to create a better society and are reviewed continuously to ensure they stay up to date with developments in society and the challenges of today. They generally fall into these categories: research ethics, business ethics, and ethics in interpersonal relationships.
- SINTEF is a member of the UN Global Compact and Transparency International, and SINTEF's ethics are guided by the principles highlighted by these organisations, as well as based on the regulations of the national ethics committees, the principles promoted by the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies (EGE), and on international conventions such as the Vancouver Convention. When dilemmas of research ethics require an assessment beyond the scope of our guidelines, our Ethics Council and Ethics Representative, we refer to statements from the EGE.
- All SINTEF's employees are expected to act in accordance with the ethical guidelines and principles. As coordinator of the WIDER UPTAKE project, SINTEF will ensure that any ethical issues, which may arise, will be handled appropriately and in a transparent and fair manner.

8 Conclusions

Formal approval and release of this deliverable within the consortium constitutes a formal commitment by partners to adhere to the DMP and the procedures it defines. When the deliverable is formally approved by the European Commission, this constitutes confirmation that the procedures are considered by the European Commission to be adequate.

As coordinator of the WIDER UPTAKE project, SINTEF will ensure that any data management issues which may arise during the project will be handled appropriately and in a transparent and fair manner.

The DMP is a living document that will expand as the project evolves and new information on data collection, generation and handling arise. Day to day data management will happen through the online tools described in this document, and through continuous collaboration between the partners responsible for data collection and generation in the project. A revised and extended version of this DMP will be prepared towards the end of the project to reflect the current status of data management in the project.

9 References

- European Commission. *H2020 Programme. Guidance for the classification of information in research projects*. Version 2.1. 26 October 2016
- European Commission. *H2020 Programme. Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020*. Version 3.0, 26 July 2016
- European Commission. *Horizon 2020 Programme. Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020*. Version 3.2, 21 March 2017
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC

Appendix A: Template for Data Processing Agreement

DATA PROCESSING AGREEMENT

Between

[ENTER DATA PROCESSOR], Company Reg. No. [xxx xxx xxx] (“the Data Processor”)

and

[ENTER CLIENT/PARTNER], Company Reg. No. [xxx xxx xxx] (“the Data Controller”)

being an agreement regarding the processing of personal data (“the Agreement”) to be performed by the Data Processor on behalf of the Data Controller as a consequence of [ENTER BACKGROUND, e.g. agreement entered into with the Data Processor as the Supplier and the Data Controller as the Client dated [date] (“the Principal Agreement”)].

1. The purpose of the agreement

The Data Processor shall process personal data on behalf of the Data Controller based on the background indicated above.

The purpose of the data processing, the duration and nature of the processing, the type of personal data to be processed and the categories of registered individuals are specified in attachments to this Agreement.

The Agreement shall ensure that personal data are processed in accordance with prevailing statutory requirements for processing personal data, including EU Directive 95/46/EF of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals relating to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, which has been implemented in Norway through Act No. 31 of 14 April 2000 relating to the processing of personal data (the Personal Data Act) and associated statutory regulations, as well as the requirements pursuant to decree of the European Parliament and Council relating to the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, superseding on 27 April 2016 Directive 95/46/EF (the Data Protection Directive), and Norwegian law and associated statutory regulations adopted pursuant to the Data Protection Directive and replacing the Norwegian Personal Data Act. Both the current and the subsequent Personal Data Act are referred to below as “the Personal Data Act”.

The Data Processor shall process the personal data as described in the Agreement, and in other ways as may be agreed in writing between the Data Processor and the Data Controller.

Terms and definitions used in the Agreement shall be construed in the same way as in the Personal Data Act.

2. The rights and obligations of the Data Controller. The obligations of the Data Processor

The Data Controller shall ensure that the relevant personal data can be processed. Specifically, Data Controllers shall ensure that adequate legal authority exists and that the agreements entered into with the registered individuals and any consents given are commensurate with and facilitate the processing of personal data as specified in Attachment 1.

The Data Processor confirms that it will implement suitable technical and organisational measures to ensure that all processing pursuant to this Agreement satisfies the requirements of the Personal Data Act with respect to the protection of the rights of the registered individual, as well as complying with all the requirements of [Article 32](#) of the Data Protection Directive. See also Section 4 for additional obligations. The Data Controller shall at all times maintain full legal ownership of the personal data.

The Data Processor shall only process personal data on the basis of written instructions received from the Data Controller. The Data Processor shall at all times be able to provide documentation of such instructions. The Data Processor shall not process personal data to which it obtains access in any other manner than is necessary to carry out the assignments it receives from the Data Controller.

The Data Processor shall assist the Data Controller in responding to requests submitted by a registered individual wishing to exercise his or her rights pursuant to Chapter III of the Data Protection Directive, taking into account the nature of the processing, also assisting as far as possible by way of suitable technical and organisational measures. The Data Processor shall also assist the Data Controller by ensuring compliance with the requirements connected with personal data security and the assessment of the consequences for personal protection and prior consultation in [Articles 32 to 36](#), taking into account the nature of the processing and the information available to the Data Processor. If approved standards of conduct exist, pursuant to [Article 40](#) of the Data Protection Directive or approved certification pursuant to [Article 42](#), with which the Data Processor has undertaken to comply or according to which it has undertaken to be certified, the Data Processor is obliged to comply with said standards of conduct or certification requirements.

The Data Processor shall maintain a log of processing activities it carries out on behalf of the Data Controller, which shall include at least the information specified by [Article 30](#) of the Data Protection Directive. The Data Controller may at any time demand to be provided with a copy of such log.

The Data Processor shall make available to the Data Controller any information necessary to demonstrate that the obligations specified in this Section 2 are fulfilled, as well as facilitating and contributing to audits, including inspections, performed by the Data Controller or any other inspector authorised by the Data Controller. This also applies to providing access to security documentation. The Data Controller itself has direct responsibility for liaison with the relevant supervisory authorities.

The Data Processor has an obligation of secrecy with regard to personal data to which it obtains access as a consequence of the Agreement and its processing of personal data, and shall ensure that persons authorised to process the personal data have undertaken to do so confidentially or are subject to appropriate statutory professional confidentiality. This provision applies also after the expiry of the Agreement.

The Data Processor shall not divulge data or information that it processes on behalf of the Data Controller to third parties without explicit instructions from the Data Controller. The Data Processor shall forward any enquiries received in this respect to the Data Controller without undue delay.

If the Data Processor is of the opinion that an instruction from the Data Controller is in conflict with the Data Protection Directive, the Personal Data Act or any other regulation regarding the processing of personal data, the Data Processor shall immediately inform the Data Controller of this. The Data Processor undertakes to discharge its obligations pursuant to the Agreement irrespective of its opinion.

3. The use of sub-vendors

When processing personal data, the Data Processor shall only use sub-vendors (data processing sub-vendors) which have been approved in writing by the Data Controller and which have been confirmed as implementing suitable technical and organisational measures to ensure that processing pursuant to this Agreement complies with the requirements of the Personal Data Act and the need to protect the rights of registered individuals.

Approved data processing sub-vendors at the time of entry into the Agreement are specified in an attachment to the Agreement.

The Data Controller grants the Data Processor general permission to use data processing sub-vendors to process personal data pursuant to the Agreement. If the Data Processor plans to use other data processing sub-vendors or substitute other data processing sub-vendors, the Data Processor shall inform the Data Controller of such plans and give the Data Controller an opportunity to oppose such changes.

Any data processing sub-vendor shall be made familiar with the obligations of the Data Processor pursuant to this Agreement and with the regulations governing the processing of the Data Controller's personal data, and shall be subject to the same obligations with regard to the protection of personal data as are stipulated in the Agreement. The data processing sub-vendor shall furnish adequate guarantees that technical and organisational measures will be adopted to ensure that its processing complies with statutory requirements. If a data processing sub-vendor fails to satisfy its obligations with regard to the protection of personal data and the requirements of the Agreement, the Data Processor shall assume full responsibility vis-à-vis the Data Controller for the sub-vendor's failure to satisfy those obligations.

4. Security and non-conformances

The Data Processor shall satisfy the requirements with regard to security measures as specified by the Personal Data Act and associated statutory regulations. The Data Processor shall be able to document its procedures and other initiatives for satisfying these requirements. The documentation shall be made available to the Data Controller on request.

Security audits shall be carried out regularly at times agreed by the parties to the Agreement. An audit may embrace a review of procedures, random inspections, more comprehensive local inspections and other appropriate verification measures. Agreement shall be reached with regard to the Data Controller's obligation to cover the cost of any use of personnel and resources necessary in connection with the performance of such audits.

In the event of breach of security or personal protection stipulations, the Data Processor shall notify the Data Controller without undue delay. Such notification shall include at least the following:

1. A description of the nature of the breach of personal data security, including, wherever possible, the categories and approximate number of registered individuals affected, and the categories and approximate number of personal data records affected,
2. the name and contact details of the personal protection advisor or any other contact site at which additional information may be obtained,
3. a description of the probable consequences of the breach of personal data security,
4. a description of the measures taken or proposed to handle the breach, including where relevant measures for reducing any adverse effects resulting from the breach.

If all the information cannot be provided in the first instance, it shall be provided successively as soon as it becomes available.

The Data Controller is responsible for submitting notification to the supervisory authority and the Data Processor shall not submit such notification nor contact the supervisory authority unless instructed to do so by the Data Controller.

5. Transfer of data to foreign countries

Personal data shall only be transmitted to third countries outside the EU or EEA according to instructions from the Data Controller. The Data Processor shall therefore not transmit, or allow parties in third countries in any way to obtain access to, personal data without explicit prior approval and instructions to this effect from the Data Controller. Consent and instructions must specify the countries to which the information may be transmitted. Even with consent and instructions, transfer to third countries shall only take place on condition that the requirements regarding security and the protection of the rights of the registered individuals pursuant to the Personal Data Act and other rules are satisfied.

6. The duration of the Agreement, termination orders, obligations in the event of expiry or cancellation

The Agreement is valid as long as the Data Processor processes or has access to personal data on behalf of the Data Controller pursuant to the Principal Agreement.

In the event of breach of this Agreement, the Personal Data Act or other relevant rules, the Data Controller is entitled to order the Data Processor to cease processing of the information with immediate effect.

On completion of the services connected with processing, the Data Processor shall, as instructed by the Data Controller, delete or return any personal data to the Data Controller and delete all existing copies unless required by law to continue to store the personal data. This also applies to any back-up copies, where it is enough to overwrite according to established routines for back-up creation.

The Data Controller shall receive written confirmation from the Data Processor that all personal data have been returned or deleted according to the instructions of the Data Controller, and that the Data Processor has not retained copies, printouts or personal data in any other form.

7. Other obligations and rights

Other obligations and rights ensue from the Principal Agreement between the Data Processor and the Data Controller regarding the services that necessitate the processing of personal data, and from this Agreement. The same contact representatives will serve in connection with this Agreement as for the Principal Agreement.

This Agreement shall not expand the Data Controller's right to impose sanctions, including the Data Processor's liability for damages, beyond the rights pursuant to the Principal Agreement.

In the event of conveyance of the Principal Agreement to other parties, this Agreement shall be conveyed correspondingly.

_____. _____ 20XX

The Data Processor

The Data Controller

NAME

NAME

Two original copies of this Agreement have been prepared, of which each party has received one.

Attachments

The purpose of processing

[The purpose and intention of the processing shall be entered here.]

The duration of the processing

[Enter the length of time the processing shall take. If the processing is according to an agreement between the parties, the duration shall be expressed as “The processing shall last for as long as the Data Processor provides services to the Data Controller pursuant to the Principal Agreement.]

The nature of the processing

[Specify here what the processing consists of, for example, “Storage of personal data” or whatever circumstances necessitate the processing pursuant to the Principal Agreement.]

Types of personal data to be processed

The following types of personal data shall be processed pursuant to the Agreement:

[Enter the type of personal data, e.g. personal name, e-mail address, telephone number, etc. It is not necessary to give details of the information to be processed, only *the type* of information.]

Categories of registered individuals

[Specify categories of registered individuals, such as employees, clients, etc.]

Data processing sub-vendors at the time of entry into the Agreement

[Specify data processing sub-vendors and countries in which the data will be processed]